

TRENDS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE SERVICE SECTOR IN THE CONTEXT OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY

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Abstract. *The article examines the improvement of existing approaches to the principles of state regulation of the economy at all levels of management, taking into account the current state of development of the transport complex, servitization and the formation of the sharing economy to change business models and develop the service sector. Fundamental changes occurring under the influence of each of the listed trends have been identified and a list of characteristics of the current state of the service sector has been compiled.*

The factors determining the high pace of development of the service sector are identified and disclosed, among which one of them is the study of world experience in the field of state regulation of the transport system in order to indicate the feasibility of state intervention in the operation of transport. Mechanisms have also been identified to help optimize the development of transport, which will contribute to the full development of the industry.

Keywords: *transport system, public administration, state regulation, budget financing of the transport sector, principles of strategic planning for transport development, international transport corridors, social norms and standards, deregulation of the transport sector.*

Annotatsiya. *Maqolada transport sohasini rivojlantirish, servislashtirish va zamonaviy iqtisodiyotni shakllantirishning hozirgi holatini hisobga olgan holda, xizmat ko'rsatish sohasini davlat tomonidan tartibga solish tamoyillarini takomillashtirish ko'rib chiqildi. Har bir sanab o'tilgan tendentsiyalar ta'sirida yuzaga keladigan tub o'zgarishlar aniqlandi va xizmat ko'rsatish sohasining hozirgi holatining xususiyatlari tahlil qilindi.*

Maqolada xizmat ko'rsatish sohasini rivojlantirishning yuqori sur'atlarini belgilovchi omillar aniqlangan va ochib berilgan, ulardan biri transport tizimini davlat tomonidan tartibga solish sohasidagi jahon tajribasini o'rganishdir. Shuningdek, transport sohasi rivojini optimallashtirishga yordam beradigan mexanizmlar ham belgilab qo'yildi, bu esa sohaning to'liq rivojlanishiga xizmat qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: *transport tizimi, davlat boshqaruvi, davlat tomonidan tartibga solish, transport sohasini byudjet tomonidan moliyalashtirish, transportni strategik rivojlantirishni rejalashtirish tamoyillari, xalqaro transport yo'laklari, ijtimoiy norma va standartlar, transportni qayta tartibga solish.*

Аннотация. *В статье рассмотрено совершенствование существующих подходов к принципам государственного регулирования экономики на всех уровнях управления с учетом текущего состояния развития транспортного комплекса, сервитизации и формирования шеринг-экономики на изменение бизнес-моделей и развитие сферы услуг. Идентифицированы фундаментальные изменения, происходящие под влиянием каждой из перечисленных тенденций и сформирован перечень характеристик современного состояния сферы услуг.*

Выявлены и раскрыты факторы, определяющие высокие темпы развития сферы услуг, среди которых одним из них является изучение мирового опыта в сфере государственного регулирования деятельности транспортной системы с целью обозначения целесообразности вмешательства государства в работу транспорта.

Также выявлены механизмы, способствующие оптимизации развития транспорта, которые будут благоприятствовать полноценному развитию отрасли.

***Ключевые слова:** транспортная система, государственное управление, бюджетное финансирование, стратегическое планирование, международные транспортные коридоры, социальные нормы и нормативы, дерегулирование.*

INTRODUCTION

Currently, the service sector (from trade and transport to financing, insurance and various types of intermediation) is one of the most promising, fast-growing types of economic activity. In our country, the sphere of transport services and economic activities is developing dynamically. Innovation is of paramount importance to improve the quality of transport services, since almost any organization uses its own or leased vehicles. The most important areas of innovative activity in transport are associated with the use of modern technologies for organizing transportation, automation and informatization of all links of the transport chain, primarily customer service processes. Important criteria for assessing the effectiveness of using innovations in the field of transport services are the dynamics of the use of energy-saving technologies, automated systems, saving time and minimizing the cost of delivering goods with high reliability of transportation.

Transport services are a business that can be very profitable and interesting. In conditions of high market saturation with a variety of services, only a business that pays sufficient attention to innovation can become successful. As a rule, companies that offer new services, the use of new transport or special conditions of transportation are more successful. High quality work and the search for new solutions make it possible to create a positive image of the company and make its reputation impeccable, and this is precisely the calling card of almost any organization that strives for success. The transition of the transport complex to an innovative path of development requires the large-scale implementation of new technologies.

ANALYSIS AND EVALUATION. Over the years of independence, large-scale structural and institutional reforms in transport have been carried out in the republic. State programs for the denationalization and privatization of transport facilities are being gradually implemented, and a consistent transition from direct administrative control to state regulation of market entities continues. To date, the legal framework for transport activities in market conditions has basically been created. Uzbekistan is one of the participants in international integration and a full-fledged subject of global economic processes.

Currently, transport accounts for 8% of the country's GDP, 17.6% of fixed assets, 1.5% of those employed in the economy, 30% of paid services provided to the population [1]. Over the past 17 years, the average annual increase in transport services has been 2.1% for freight transportation and 5% for passenger transportation. At the same time, the growth rate of transport services is not the same by type of transport. Personal vehicles today have taken over part of the cargo and passenger traffic of mass public transport, not only from short-distance and suburban lines, but also from long-distance routes. In the market for passenger transport services, there is a continuous redistribution of passenger flows between alternative modes of transport, based on their ability to satisfy the effective demand of various segments of the population. The ongoing acceleration of economic growth and the improvement in living standards in Uzbekistan have had a positive impact on the volume of passenger traffic.

Passenger turn over of all types of transport in the republic in 2019 increased compared to the 2010 level. by 84.2% (Table 1). At the same time, there is a significant increase in the volume of air (89.6%) and road (85.9%) transport. Population mobility (average number of passenger-km

per year) over these years has increased from 2.9 to 4.2 thousand passenger-km per inhabitant. For comparison, we note that in 2012. it (in thousand pass-km per person) was: in the USA - 12.7, in Germany - 8.2, Japan - 4.2, in Russia - 4.2. However, the COVID-19 pandemic has made its negative contribution, especially in the service industries, resulting in passenger turnover decreased by 16.7%. There is not such a significant increase in the dynamics of cargo turnover. Thus, in 2019, freight turnover increased by only 20.1% compared to 2010, while road transportation increased by only 0.2%, rail - by 20.2%, pipeline - 34.8%. their intensive growth in road (78% compared to 2010) and pipeline (43%) modes of transport, and in air – a decline of 43% (Table 1). The slow increase in freight turnover on railways (5.4%) is associated with a reduction in the average transportation distance here [1]. The pandemic affected freight transport less than passenger transport. Recession in 2020 turned out to be 5.2% compared to the previous year.

From 2000 to 2019, the operational length of public railway tracks increased by 1,564 km and at the beginning of 2020. amounted to 4735.1 km. The density of railways and road networks is slightly higher than in Russia and Kazakhstan, but much lower than in developed countries. (Table 1). Indicators of countries' provision of transport routes differ depending on the density of communications routes, on the one hand, and, on the other hand, on the scale of economic and social development of the country (B, in the form of GDP in PPP, \$ billion) taking into account the territory it occupies (S), population (N). When considering the indicators of countries' provision with an integrated transport network (Lin) in relation to the product $3\sqrt{(NSB)}$, one can see a slightly different picture.

Table 1
Indicators of the provision of individual countries with the railway and road networks as of 2023. [2]

Countries	Territory, thousand square meters km, (S)	Population thousand people (N)	GDP in PPP, \$ billion (B)	Average value $(3\sqrt{(NSB)})$	Length of the transport network, thousand km			Average density of the transport network, km		
					railways (Lrail)	highways (LA)	integrated transport network (Lin=Lrail+0.1LA)	railways (Lrail)	highways (LA)	integrated transport networks (Lin/3√NSB)
Uzbekistan	447,4	33581	235	15227,2	6,5	183,5	24850	14,53	410,15	1,63
Kazakhstan	2717,3	18777	487,9	29198,8	16,6	168,7	33470	6,11	62,08	1,15
Turkmenistan	488,1	6031	112,76	6923,9	3,6	55,6	9160	7,38	113,91	1,32
Kyrgyzstan	198,5	6524	33,9	3527,7	0,4	18,5	2250	2,02	93,20	0,64
Tajikistan	143,1	9538	31,5	3503,2	0,6	27,8	3380	4,19	194,27	0,96
Russia	17075,4	145934	3968,2	214638,2	86,6	1542,2	240820	5,07	90,32	1,12
China	9596,96	1439324	2526,6	77635,2	124	5012,5	625250	12,92	522,30	0,92
India	3287,59	1380004	9229,2	347248,7	67,4	5903,3	657730	20,50	1795,63	1,89
Iran	1648	83992	1491	59095,9	12,3	214	33700	7,46	129,85	0,57
Türkiya	780,58	84339	2350	53683,1	12	236,6	35660	15,37	303,11	0,66
Japan	377,835	126476	5231,1	62994,3	27,3	1280	155300	72,25	3387,72	2,47

England	244,101	67886	3121,1	37258,0	17,7	397	57400	72,51	1626,38	1,54
France	547,03	65274	3097,1	47999,4	29,9	1090,2	138920	54,66	1992,94	2,89
Germany	357,022	83784	4473,8	51149,8	43,5	644,5	107950	121,84	1805,21	2,11
Italy	301,23	60462	2557,4	35979,9	24,2	487,7	72970	80,34	1619,03	2,03
Spain	504,782	46755	1924,7	35680,6	15,9	683,2	84220	31,50	1353,46	2,36
USA	9372,61	331003	20575	399647,8	257,7	7150	972700	27,50	762,86	2,43

All this is already holding back the development of the economy, creating a serious threat of slowing down the overall economic growth of the republic and weakening its position in the world market. In the transport industry of Uzbekistan as a whole and its individual sub-sectors, a number of unresolved problems have developed and remain open:

- there is no necessary coordination and complexity in managing the development and functioning of the transport system;

- transport intensity of GDP (adjusted ton-km per unit of GDP), although it has decreased more than three times over the years of independence, it remains high in comparison with developed countries;

- insufficient use of the geopolitical state and transit potential of the republic, which is due to the lack of communication along the shortest routes of the country’s railways with the railways of India and China;

- the condition and pace of development of roads, especially in rural areas, do not correspond to established standards and the growth rate of motorization;

- the share of railways in the transport services market is clearly insufficient, especially in the development of massive freight and passenger flows in domestic communications;

- the share of single-track railways is 88% of the total length of communication routes, which reduces the maneuverability and mobility of railway transportation, especially when transporting expensive export goods;

- the presence of different railway gauge standards at cross-border stations leads to large financial, time and other losses during international transport;

- the technological level of transport systems does not sufficiently ensure the established technical regulations and requirements for their safe operation;

- measures for state support of transport industries have greatly weakened, and the excessive presence of the state in the activities of transport enterprises has increased significantly;

In the last decades of the 20th century, transport policy took a leading place among the main directions of the socially oriented strategy of developed countries, aimed at increasing the efficiency of the national economy, which began to be measured not by traditional quantitative indicators, but by qualitative indicators, primarily the level of quality of life of the population. At the same time, the efficiency of transport, as a special sector of the economy, in Western countries is measured not only by an increase in its own operational or financial and economic indicators, but also expressed by the degree of participation in the economic and social life of society. Therefore, such forms of organization of market relations as transport and logistics are increasingly used, and transport becomes an integral participant in the logistics conveyor of cargo and passenger movement and works for the overall economic and social effect [9].

The share of transport in the GDP of most countries fluctuates between 3-9%, and in the number of employed - 3-8%. These data do not include individual and institutional transport, which further increases the importance of transport services in the economy, especially if there is

a significant informal sector. Typically, the share of transport services in GDP decreases as national income increases. It is highest in Asian countries, then in Latin America and Africa. Employment in transport in the 1980s increased mainly in countries of the global periphery [10]. State regulation of transport activities and state financing of individual elements of the transport system and types of transport activities in market conditions remain an objective necessity. The transport strategy should be based on the principle of separating the tasks of state regulation of the industry and the performance of economic functions by private entrepreneurs.

The unity of the transport system in the process of managing this sector of the economy presupposes its development on uniform principles of institutional regulation of all types of transport, coordination of the development of all types of transport infrastructure, a balanced distribution of budget resources between different types of transport, as well as regulation of competition between different companies in the transport services market. Using common approaches and principles, it is necessary to harmonize interests and unite the efforts of the state and business in the field of transport, coordinate the provision of transport means to the national security and defense capability of the country, as well as the formation of a single information space in transport. The economic basis for the functioning of the transport system is the principle of competition between independent operators and suppliers of transport services and transport infrastructure services. The state must cease its participation in competitive markets as an entrepreneur of transport services. In terms of transport infrastructure services, it is necessary to commercialize its use and attract private operators to its creation and operation. In the future, a phased privatization of individual elements of the transport infrastructure is possible.

In the national goals and objectives in the field of sustainable development for the period until 2030, approved by the Cabinet of Ministers, within the framework of the Development Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021, they are set, in particular, in Goal 11 “Ensuring openness, safety, resilience and environmental sustainability of cities and populated areas” points" set Target 11.2: "by 2030, ensure access to safe, affordable, accessible and environmentally sustainable transport systems by improving road safety, in particular increasing the use of public transport, paying special attention to the needs of socially vulnerable segments of the population [12].

The totality of the above indicators of final consumption of transport services constitutes the so-called social norms for the consumption of transport services, recommended by national standards and other regulations of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Social norms and standards determine the level of implementation of constitutional rights and guarantees of citizens, regulate the social protection of clients and the formation of sectors of the social sphere. These standards are intended for regulatory authorities as a social guideline both for the purpose of improving the quality of life and regulating the level of transport services in the regions. Regional characteristics and differences in the levels of economic and social development of regions suggest a differentiated approach to the territorial location of the core transport network, the formation of which is carried out based on the characteristics of (1) the extraterritoriality of its location and (2) the priority of ensuring the passage of transit flow along the shortest routes with (3) bypass largest transport hubs. The basis of the spatial model for the development of transport infrastructure in Uzbekistan is the national sections of the ITC. In the future, with the development and deepening of market relations in the country, the participation of the state in the market of transport services as an operator should be replaced by a phased privatization of infrastructure with the imposition of its owners with specific obligations to the state.

Recently, work has begun in Uzbekistan on the formation of private and joint-stock airlines and airports. Work on the formation of international logistics centers on the railways in Tashkent, Chinaz, Termez and a number of other regions with non-state ownership has also intensified to a significant extent. For the sustainable functioning of the transport sector, it is necessary, first of all, to improve antimonopoly regulation and a phased transition from price regulation to a market of free prices in the market sector of the market. This is especially important for railway transport, where the opinion about the supposedly absolutely stable natural monopoly position of the industry has become established. At the same time, in world practice, for example, in the USA, it is known that almost all railways are private, their number is more than 560, of which 7 are vertically integrated, private regional companies - 33 and private local companies - more than 500. Only one The unitary state company AMTRAK provides long-distance passenger services [15].

President of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev, in his address to the Oliy Majlis on January 25, 2020, indicated: “In the railway sector, it is necessary to differentiate between the transportation of passengers and goods, operation and maintenance, that is, to highlight the natural monopoly part and separately develop those areas where the private sector can be attracted ” [16]. State unitary enterprises that compete with private operators in the transport services market must consistently be privatized. At the same time, the state retains responsibility for the safety of the transport process, the state of transport infrastructure and the provision of transport services in sectors where the market is not yet sufficiently developed. It is based on the principle of eliminating unnecessary interference in the management of transportation activities, both in the field of transport entrepreneurship and in certain issues of regulation of the sphere. Gradual deregulation of the transport sector is considered one of the important ways to demonopolize it. Recognizing the entire railway infrastructure as a sphere of natural monopoly, it is necessary to recognize the relevance of strengthening the competitive position of the railway company, both in the domestic and foreign markets of transport services.

CONCLUSION

Innovative activities in the service sector, including in the field of transport services, must be associated with a predictable result, which leads to changes both within the organization and in the external environment. Expanding needs in the service sector determines transformations in the production process of commodity producers and in information systems. The development of the service sector creates a new competitive environment and new needs for goods and services. Innovative activities in the service sector are an integral part of effective production and market activities, since it is precisely this that ensures the strategic sustainability of companies in a rapidly developing services market. It is becoming increasingly clear that the service sector can provide significant employment growth both today and in the future, and become a “locomotive” of economic growth.

Transport, along with other infrastructure sectors, provides the basic conditions for the life of society, being an important tool for achieving social, economic, and foreign policy goals. Transport is not only an industry specializing in the movement of goods and people, first of all, it is an intersectorial system that transforms living and economic conditions. Sustainable development of transport is a guarantee of the unity of the economic space, free movement of goods and services, competition and freedom of economic activity, improvement of the living conditions and standard of living of the population. Every transport company must realize that without the introduction of innovative technologies it is extremely difficult to remain a market participant.

The full use of foreign instruments of state regulation of the transport sector of Uzbekistan is limited, in our opinion, by the insufficient development of public administration institutions at the regional level, the country's incompletely developed unified transport system, as well as a significant gap between the planned results of the industry's development and those actually achievable in the current political and economic conditions. conditions indicators.

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